

First IRRI Alumni Association

Dr. Yookti Sarikaphuti, IRRI Trustee from Thailand, suggested that IRRI alumni from different countries should form associations, which might become important promoters of agricultural development. The first group is the Thai-IRRI Alumni Association. Its first president, Suvit Pushphavesa, was elected 12 Apr 1984 at a special dinner at Rama Gardens, which Dr. Yookti and about 60 IRRI alumni and staff attended.

Some of the very first Thai trainees and scholars were at the dinner. Among them were Damkheong Chandrapana (1968), Saner Puranabhavung (1963), Sanga Duangratana (1964), Sompom Patanakamjorn (1962), Wittaya Seetanun (1969), Sukhee Sornchai (1962), and Paibool Trachoo (1962). IRRI has trained more than 350 Thai scientists.

Similar alumni associations are being formed in Pakistan and the Philippines. The associations will celebrate IRRI's 25th anniversary, in 1985, with special activities. □

IRRI-developed variety named in the Philippines

At its 29th meeting, the Philippine Seed Board named IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2 as IR62, and recommended it for cultivation in irrigated lowland areas of the Philippines. IR62 is similar to IR36 in growth duration, grain quality, and yield potential, but has more lodging and tungro resistance. It is resistant to all known brown planthopper biotypes. Parents of IR62 are PTB33, IR30, and IR36.

Velusamy wins award for thesis

R. Velusamy, postdoctoral fellow in the IRRI Entomology Department, was awarded the 1983 National Gold Medal for the best doctoral thesis among crop protection disciplines in India. His thesis was titled "Resistance in rice to the brown planthopper."

Velusamy is an associate professor of entomology at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India. His major advisor, S. Chelliah, was an IRRI post-doctoral fellow in 1977-79. □

Roger honored by France

P. A. Roger, senior scientist of ORSTOM, the French organization for scientific research and development, and IRRI soil microbiologist, has received the *Chevalier dans l'Ordre du Merite Agricole* from the Government of France. Among the three French orders created to recognize outstanding work in public or private office, the *Merite Agricole* recognizes contributions in agronomy.

Roger has worked in West Africa, where he conducted research on microbiological degradation of organic matter in temperate and tropical soils, and has visited IRRI twice – for 18 months in 1979-80 and from 1981 to date. At IRRI, his work has been on blue-green algae in rice fields. Roger is author of more than 50 scientific papers and coauthor of *Blue-green algae and rice*. □

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